

College Students Opinion on Selecting Mobile Service Provider in Coimbatore City

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INTRODUCTION:

Consumer behaviour is a rapidly growing field of research and teaching which ,in addition to considerable value of marketing managers and others who are professionally concerned with buying activity. An important reason for studying consumer behaviour is evaluation of consumer groups with unsatisfied needs and desires. The essence of modern marketing concept is that all elements of business should be geared for the satisfaction of consumers.The challenge to the marketers is to determine the relative influence of the various factors and to adapt and apply skilfully the so called information to a proper marketing mix. In other words, the total marketing effort must be so designed that the customer perceives its various features as providing an answer to his perceived problems and felt needs.Consumer analysis seeks to determine the underlying currents and cross currents in the customer's minds. It focus on the causes rather than the results of effective marketing strategy and tactics employed by the firms that are successful in the market.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

Consumer satisfaction is defined by Webster's dictionary as: "Fulfilment of a need or want." satisfaction is a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment, resulting from comparison of a product's perceived and actual performance in relation to his or her expectations. So, consumer's satisfaction is a function of the product's perceived performance and the consumer's expectation.Satisfaction is often a subjective phenomenon and depends on the consumer's state of mind both at the time of purchase and more

importantly at the time of consumption. It is important because in large number of cases, some degree of post purchase dissonance is evident among consumer. Many companies are aiming at high satisfaction because customers who are just satisfied find it easy to switch when a better offer come along. Those who are highly satisfied are much less ready to switch. In fact, emphasis has shifted from mere satisfaction to delight of customers. High satisfaction or delight creates an emotional affinity with the brand and the supplier, not just a rational preference. The result is high customer loyalty. Hence the present study is carried out to study the College Students opinion on selecting their Mobile Service Provider in Coimbatore City.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The following were the objectives of the present study;

1. To study the Students opinion towards mobile service providers in Coimbatore City.
2. To evaluate the major service provider which satisfied the customer.
3. To assess the needs, requirements, and expectations of the customer.
4. To study and identify how the customers are benefited from the mobile service providers.

METHODOLOGY:

Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. It may be understood as science of studying how research is done. “The study of methods by which we gain knowledge, it idea with the cognitive process imposed on research by the problems arising from the nature of its subject-matter”.

Research Design

Research Design adopted in the present study is Descriptive Research Design.

Sample size

Sample size refer to the numbers of respondents researcher have selected for the survey. Researchers have selected 50 College Students in Coimbatore City for the present study as sample..

Sampling technique

The reserchers have selected 50 College students for the present study through Convenience Sampling Technique. Area of the study

Period of the study

The research has undertaken during the period of January 2020 to March 2020.

Data collection

The researchers have framed a well structured Closed ended questions consisting of 20 statements for the survey. The questionnaire were circulated among the respondents and the data were collected.

Sources of Data

The data for the present study were collected directly from the respondents through questionnaire.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

- The study covers only 50 students.
- The research has limited time to collect data.
- Able to cover only those students who were currently studying.

ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS:

The data which were coolected through questionnaire were analysed using simple percentage analysis and the results were as follows;

- 24% of respondents belonged to 3G network, 76% of respondents belonged to 4G network.
- 92% of respondent belonged to prepaid connection and 8% of respondent belonged to post-paid connection.
- 48% of respondent belonged to Airtel network and 52% of respondent belonged to others network.
- 12% of respondent belonged to the range of spending for mobile to rupees 51 to 100 and 48% of respondent belonged to the spending range more than rupees 200.
- 90% of respondent belonged to others and only 10% of respondent belonged to sms rates.
- 6% of respondent selected the scheme based on the poster at shop and 36% of respondent selected based on advertisement and others through their friends recommendations.
- 52% of respondent took their own decision in selecting schemes and service provider and 48% of respondent have taken decision based on their family members opinion .
- 54% of respondent depend on the nearest retailer and 22% of respondent depend on company outlet and the remaining 12% used other modes.
- 72% of respondent rated the services of the provider as good 6% of respondent rated as poor and the remaining 22% were neutral in this issue.
- 16% of respondent felt that they are facing problem for internet in their mobile service provider and 44% of respondent felt that they have network problem with their service provider and 40% were neutral in this. .
- 40% of respondent were satisfied with their service provider, 12% were very much satisfied with their service provider and remaining 48% were not satisfied with their service provider.

- 16% of respondent use this service provider services because it is essential for business, 60% of respondent use for personal requirement and 24% for both business and personal usage.
- 12% of respondent select service provider based on quality, 30% of respondent select based on coverage and the remaining 58% select the service provider based on brand image.

CONCLUSION:

The competition among companies increased, so it is a must for the firm to improve its services to maintain its current customers . The coming days are very competitive for telecommunication sector industries. So the company in the field must be vigilant and competitive for maintaining and improving the market. As per my belief we have seen that the choice of mobile handset and services cannot be separated came out true because when we tried to find out the customer decision. We successfully classified customers in to eight group each with some special requirement service wise and handsets attribute wise. Competition in telecom industry is heating up its time for Indian telecom players also to align up in the new dynamic business environment. Telecom majors should think to launch the product according to the needs of customers to satisfy them brand loyal as very soon this blue ocean of Indian telecom scenario will convert into red ocean where the loss of is the gain of other. They also think of searching new space or we can say either creating a new blue space to sustain their growth in long run

References:

- ❖ Debnath “Analyzing Growth of Cellular Telecom Sector and Understanding Consumer performance and choices on the uses of cell phone,”Indian journal of marketing 2002”pb-27-51
- ❖ Hatt ,“Role of Competition in Growing Market: Telecom Sector”, Indian Journal of Marketing, September 2003, PP 8 – 16.
- ❖ **Jha**; “Customers’ Attitude towards Cell phoneServices in Communication System”, Indian Journal of Marketing, March, 2004, PP 33 -37.